

2-3% fetal calf serum in cell media is sufficient for development and growth of human mononuclear cell cultures

Sudhir Bhatia, Genekam Biotechnology AG, Duissernstr. 65a, 47358 Duisburg, Germany.

Email: anfrage@genekam.de

Summary: It is a common practice that 10-20% fetal calf serum (FCS) is being used in the cell culture media for development and maintaining of human mononuclear cells as well as other cell cultures. FCS is produced with a painful process for animals and is one of major cost factor. The reduction in volume of FCS can make it less unethical and reduce the costs strongly. Therefore 2-3% FCS is used in development of different mononuclear cell cultures and different parameters like morphology, production of antibodies, isolation of DNA/DNA and magnetic beads cell isolations were tested. It was found that there was no difference between 10% FCS and 2-3% FCS containing media in the above said parameters. More than hundred such cell cultures were developed and many of them were maintained more than 3 years. Conclusion is that 2-3% FCS is sufficient for development and maintaining of human mononuclear cell cultures.

Keywords: Mononuclear cells, cell culture, Fetal calf serum, ELISA

Background: In all laboratories around the world, it is common practice to use 10% of fetal calf serum (FCS) in cell cultures like mononuclear cells, stem cells etc. (Leshem 1999, Mannello et al 2007, Witzender et al 2013, Messias et al 2019, Alipour et al 2020, Bhatia 2022, Juhl et al 2021) This practice is being conducted for last many years. (Enders, 1953, Nowell 1960) Manufacturing of FCS needs processing of serum from unborn fetus. This process involves steps, which may be called unethical according to animal rights because the heart of unborn slaughtered animal is being punctured to get the FCS, which causes a lot of discomfort to animals and it is filtered to make it sterile. (Jochems et al 2002, van der Valk et al 2017). Hence there is a lot of research going for development of alternatives. (van der Valk et al 2017, Venkatesan et al. 2022). The FCS is continuously used because its demand is increasing. As 10 to 20% FCS is being used in processes involving the development and maintaining of the cell cultures, hence FCS is one of the major costs of cell cultures producing different proteins or during the conducting of cell culture research. These concepts of using 10-20% FCS is coming from publications from very old days; therefore, we decided to try and make studies to use the low concentration 2-3% in the development and maintenance of different human mononuclear cell cultures.

Methods: Human buffy coat (Red Cross blood collection center) was obtained, the mononuclear cells were isolated with two different methods. One method was density gradient method. In this method, the buffy coat was mixed with equal volume of PBS in 50 ml sterile plastic tube. In another 50 ml sterile plastic tube, 30 ml of density gradient solution (Biochrome) were added. To this, 20 ml of diluted buffy coated were poured in such a way that buffy coat makes a new layer on density gradient solution and it should not mix with density gradient solution. This was centrifuged at 19000 rpm for 20 minutes to get a layer of white blood cells on the density gradient solution. These cells were removed and collected in another 50 ml sterile tube. The collected cells were washed 3 times with PBS and centrifuged as mentioned above. After that the cells stained with trypan blue solution (Biochrome) were counted in Neuberger chamber under the microscope.

These cells were cultured in different concentrations in 6 wells and 96 wells plate with different cell counts in media made of 10% and 2-3% FCS in DMEM or RPMI containing 1% of Streptopenicillin (Biochrome) antibiotics as well as 1% Glutamine (Biochrome). DMEM and RPMI were used from 2 different manufacturers, which are Biochrome and Lonza. FCS was supplied from Biochrome.

Mononuclear cells were kept in CO₂ incubator at 37 °C as they were cultured starting from 5 x 10⁶ cells per well. They were fed regularly. The Samples of the media were taken from these culture cells for testing purposes e.g., the presence of antibodies as well as cells were used to select the specific cells through the specific magnetic beads for further culturing. The isolated cells were observed under fluorescent microscope (Zeiss). The cell cultures were observed under microscope regularly. These cells were sub cultured in cell culture flasks. The presence of antibodies was done with ELISA as well as magnetic beads ELISA kits (Genekam). DNA/RNA from these cell cultures were isolated successfully with mini column isolation kits (Genekam) for testing the confirmation of successful isolation of RNA/DNA with real time PCR kit as well as conventional PCR test (Genekam) for internal control like β-actin and β-globin genes. These isolated RNA were used in PCR to find the presence of antibodies specific genes in gel agarose.

A part of mononuclear cells from each cell culture was taken out and centrifuged. They were stored in freezing media (Genekam) at -20 C and later on shifted in liquid nitrogen tank. Some of cell cultures were thawed and cultured again.

Alternatively, a new and simple method was used to isolate the mononuclear cells, where one mix two different components and let it stay till the erythrocytes are lysed. (Manuscript in preparation)

Results: In year 2013, we conducted the comparison between 2-3% and 10% FCS cell culture media and found no difference in the performance for different parameters, therefore our laboratory shifted to use of 2-3% FCS cell culture media. We have made more than different hundred mononuclear cells cultures with 2-3% FCS cell cultures, we get always good performance. The cell cultures look healthy and good under microscope in Neubauer chamber. (Picture 1 and 2) ELISA performed showed the presence of specific antibodies e.g., Chlamydia. The cells can be sub cultured in flasks of many different volumes for last many years. (Picture 3). We isolated the specific cells e.g., plasma cells with anti CD27 specific magnetic beads, they were observed under microscope and cultured in flasks. (Picture 4)

The cells were cultured in different concentration starting from 5 x 10⁶ cells per well and they show always good performance in 2-3% FCS cell cultures. The results of 20 experiments as example were presented here, where these cells were examined under microscope for phenotype, where it was found that these cells are healthy. They were tested, whether they are producing the antibodies, it was found that these cell cultures were producing human antibodies as tested with ELISA. Successful isolations of DNA / RNA were confirmed through β-actin and β-Globin internal control during the real time and conventional PCR. (Graphic 1) Many cell cultures were kept for more than 2 years without loss of morphology except that some of mononuclear cells sticks on plastic floor of plates and flasks very strongly. The thawing of frozen cell culture led to obtain healthy mononuclear cell cultures.

Discussion: we are showing here that 2-3% FCS in DMEM and RPMI media are sufficient to culture the human mononuclear cells for different purposes e.g., production of antibodies, isolation of specific populations like CD27 as well as isolation of RNA/DNA for molecular analysis. Our laboratory is using this for last 10 years and we have developed more than 100 different cell cultures. It was found that some authors have used also 2% as well as 4%. (Suchanek et al. 2013), but these are very rare reports in literature. Cultured mononuclear cells were used to conduct the presence of tumor markers also. (Data not shown)

2-3% FCS is sufficient to maintain the human mononuclear cell cultures, this helps to cut costs of doing research. In case of industrial production, this work should help to reduce the costs of cell cultures, which should lead in reduction in the production costs and development of cost-effective therapies, vaccines and diagnostics. This work can contribute to reduce the pain caused to animals. We have used this media to isolate and maintain mesenchymal stem cells successfully. (Data not shown; Bhatia 2021). This research work will lead to save money in many institutes.

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Picture 1 showing the human mononuclear cells under microscope in Neubauer chamber

Picture 2 is showing mononuclear cells, which looks healthy and huge in number under microscope.

Picture 3 is showing human mononuclear cells in cell culture media after 2 months of culturing.

Picture 4 is showing mononuclear cells successfully isolated with magnetic beads under microscope.

Graphic 1 is showing the results of different parameters studied during 20 different experiments.